

THE PASTORAL COUNSELLORS

JOURNAL *of* **NIGERIAN ASSOCIATION OF PASTORAL COUNSELLORS**

In collaboration with
Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies
and
Department of Guidance and Counselling
LEAD CITY UNIVERSITY, IBADAN, NIGERIA

VOL. 3. MAY 2024

ISSN: PRINT 2971-5199 ONLINE 2971-5202

Editors in Chief
Professor Samson Fatokun
Professor Donald A. ODELEYE

Managing Editors
Professor Isaiah ABOLARIN
Olabisi T. Precious KILLIAN PhD

Corresponding Editor
Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI PhD

Jethro's Counsels in Exodus 18:17-23: Lessons for Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church Leaders in Ilorin Metropolis

Prof. Afolorunso Olalekan DAIRO

Department of Religious Studies and Philosophy, Redeemer's University, Ede, Osun State.

dairoa@run.edu.ng, +2348034001020

Tosin Success ABOLAJI

Department of Religious Studies and Philosophy, Redeemer's University, Ede, Osun State

successabolaji@gmail.com, +2348136126006

Abstract

Counselling is a therapeutic measure through the use of communication skills. In the Old Testament, counselling is used as a medium to helping someone in distress, proffer solutions and give necessary insights to solving problems. Moses led the children of Israel out of Egypt without an administrative plan of overseeing the large congregation of the Israelites community. The study examined Jethro's counsel to Moses in Exodus 18:17-23 and lessons for Nigerian Pentecostal Church Leaders in Ilorin Metropolis. The workloads on Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church Leaders in Ilorin Metropolis are enormous, and as a result pose threat to their health, effective church administration and wellbeing as Church Leaders. The study adopted exegetical, historical and participatory observation methods. It was discovered that Indigenous Pentecostal Church Leaders in Ilorin Metropolis engage in several activities such as the Church weekly services and the Sunday services. They also chair and oversee virtually all units in the Church, and hold important leadership position among other Christian fellowship in their neighbourhoods. Therefore, the study recommended that the Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church leaders in Ilorin Metropolis should engage in division of labour among members for effective church administration and reduction in health hazard.

Keywords: Exodus 18:17-23, Ilorin Metropolis, Indigenous Pentecostal Church Leaders, Jethro's Counsel, Moses

Introduction

The history of the children of Israel remains at the core viewpoint of biblical history and the world at large. This owes to the premises that the Israelites were God's chosen people through whom God's divine purpose (the redemptive plan) was brought to fulfilment thus affording the biblical Israel the pride of place in biblical times and the history of the modern Christianity. The Pentateuch which was the Greek version of the Torah (Law) becomes a reference since many centuries till now. These books also pictured the origin of human leadership and the loopholes in the supposed perfect man's administration. It can be said that, leadership trait and tendency was an in-built capacity since man's creation. This finds expression in the use of the word *radah* in Genesis 1:26-28 account and which according to Brown-Driver-Briggs (n.d.) means to rule or have dominion.

The narrative of Israelites history continues in the land of slavery, Egypt. Moses was introduced as God's deliverer of his people from the Egyptian bondage. Traces of his selection can be seen from the time of his birth as he was miraculously saved from the great massacre of the bloody Pharaoh (Exodus 1:22-2:1-8) and by adoption became an Egyptian prince down to the time of his first Sinaitic experience (Exo. 3). Moses' elopement to Midian was to save his life from the looming destruction and at there he met the priest, Jethro, through his daughters. He was later engaged with Zipporah in marriage (Exo. 2:20-21). Jethro's involvement in Moses' life began from the marriage with his daughter thus creating an unending relationship with the potential deliverer and leader of the Israelites.

It is important to recall that seventy people of the household of Jacob entered the land of Egypt (Gen. 46:27; Exo. 1:5). At their exodus, there were about six hundred men on foot excluding the women and the children (Exo. 12:37). Though biblical scholars such as Jeff after his mathematical approach summarized that, approximately 6,000 individuals travelled from Egypt to Mt. Sinai (Jeff, n.d.). Redford (1992) opined that since the 600,000 men were accounted for in the Exodus account, he added that the 600,000 plus wives, children, the elderly, and the "mixed multitude" of non-Israelites would have numbered some 2 to 2.5 million. The thrust of this paper is not to argue the particular number of departed Israelites but to point out a drastic shift in their number from the time of Jacob to Moses which calls for adoption of a broader pattern of administration different from the small patriarchal system used during the time of Abraham, Isaac and Jacob to a wider administrative pattern.

Moses was relatively a novice in the governance of the people, thus the observation and conclusion of Jethro which ultimately led to his counsel. Counselling according to Francis (1993) is a relationship between a professionally trained, competent counsellor and an individual seeking help in gaining greater self-understanding and improved decision making and behaviour changing skills for problem resolution and developmental growth. The view of Francis is apt to the role of Jethro's in Mosaic administration, paving way for understanding an administrative process through engaging others, in order to ensure safety of the leader and peace in the wider community. Moses embraced Jethro's counsels as identified in Exodus 18:17-23 and as he continues in his voyage to the promise land, he ensured equal representation and division of labour among the people. Church activities today are enormous and cannot be executed by a single person (pastor), thus, the need to diversify roles among members of the congregation. It is important to state that as counselling is a key to development and progress (Psalm 1:1), it can also be a tool to destruction (1 Kg. 13:18-19). Therefore, is it right to say that Nigerian Pentecostal Indigenous Church Leaders must oversee every department in the church? Is Jethro's counsel to Moses applicable to the Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church Leaders in Ilorin Metropolis? Should church administration be monopolised? All these are buttressed under, historical background of Exodus 18, Pentecostalism in Nigeria: The Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Churches, exegetical analysis of Exodus 18:17-23, lessons for Nigerian indigenous Pentecostal church leaders in Ilorin Metropolis and conclusion.

Historical Background of Exodus 18

Exodus literally means 'going out' or departure. The word itself was adopted into English (via Latin) from Greek ἔξοδος, which literally means a way out, a going out; a going out, departure, the exodus, Hebrew 11:22; met. a departure from life, decease, death, Luke 9:31; 2 Peter 1:15 (Bill Mounce, n.d.). The Greek word was formed by combining the prefix *ex-* (meaning 'out of') and *hodos*, 'road' or 'way' (*Merriam Webster Dictionary*, n.d.) Jamieson et al (1871) commented that Exodus derives its name from its being occupied principally with a relation of the exit of the Children of Israel from Egypt and the unfolding events succeeding their escape. Umaru (2023) writes:

Exodus was written down historically to preserve the stories of how the Israelites became enslaved in Egypt, their liberation, and their preservation in the Sinai desert. Theologically, the book's primary goal is divine self-disclosure because God has revealed Himself to Israel as Yahweh (Exo. 6:2-3), a name that means that Yahweh, the God of the Hebrews, will take Israel for His people and will be their God. God has not only remembered His 240 covenant promises to the Hebrew Patriarch (Exo. 6:7).

The above excerpt resonates the importance of Exodus account. Thus, it is crucial to state that the book of Exodus was a compendium that gives a link to the Israelites who lived in Egypt and the Israelites who lived in Canaan. This is not to say that there are two Israelites rather it is affirmed that the history of the Canaanite Israelites can be traced to the Egyptian bondage, therefore, establishing the salvific work of God through the Exodus account (Boaheng, 2021).

The chapter clearly expressed a moment of succeeding their deliverance from Egypt. Meyer (2005) quoted Carpenter that the Chapter 18 introduces the problem of community organization and adjudication. At the same time, it is a transitional chapter; as an epilogue to chapters 1-17 and a prologue to chapters 19-40, it is thus a bridge between the exodus story and the Sinai event. *Enduring word* (n.d.) writes:

Jethro, the priest of Midian, Moses' father-in-law, heard of all that God had done for Moses and for Israel His people: The greatness of God's work through Moses and for the people of Israel became known to surrounding peoples, especially those with an interest in Moses as Jethro. Jethro was the priest of Midian – likely a descendant of one of Abraham's other children through Keturah named Midian (Genesis 25:1-2). Because of this connection with Abraham, we have good reason to believe he was a true priest and worshipped the true God.

The foregoing shows a connection of Moses with the priest of Midian and also went further to trace the origin of the Midianites to Abraham, establishing an ancestral origin with people of Israel. It is important to state that, Moses first elopement from Egypt to Midian (Exo. 2:15) serves as a bedrock for the continuity of the relationship seen in Exodus 18. The initial was an escape from death while the later was mark of total deliverance and success of Moses and the entire congregation of Israelites from Egypt, therefore, this call for celebration. Henry (2010) commented that Jethro came to rejoice with Moses in happiness of Israel, and to bring his wife and children to him. Moses must have his family with him (Exo. 18:1-6), that while he ruled the church of God, he might set a good example in family (1 Tim 3:5).

The conversion between Moses and Jethro does not only show that they were in-laws but it also established the cordiality between both personalities. Verse 7-12 showcased the conversion concerning God's wondrous works. Henry (2010) sharply noted that Jethro not only rejoiced in the honour done to his son-in-law, but in all the goodness done to Israel. Non-Israelites were more affected with the favours God had showed to Israel, than many were who received them. The initial government collapsed (Pharaoh's government) and the New Government (Theocracy) was established under the leadership of Moses.

Pentecostalism in Nigeria: The Indigenous Pentecostal Churches

Adesayan noted that the term "Pentecostal" is from the Greek word which may refer to the modern charismatic reformation movement with a distinctive theology of the Spirit that gives doctrinal priority to the practice of spiritual gifts of tongues. Ogidiolu (2019) remarked that the term Pentecost grammatically is a word from Greek language. The word according to him is a compound word of two words: *pente* and *cost* which means fifth or fifty and celebration respectively. He further buttressed that, it is a feast of the Jews slated for fiftieth day after the Passover feast. O' Connor proposed a definition for the term Pentecostalism. The term Pentecostalism according to him means:

A movement of Christian renewal typified by the first Christian Pentecost when the Holy Spirit descending upon the fearful Apostles, transformed them into bold, ardent and convincing evangelists. It is characterized by the reappearance of the charisma of glossolalia, healing, miracles etc. (O' Connor, 1993).

From the submission of O' Connor, it can be deduced that the Holy Spirit enables, transforms and strengthen the feeble minded and wearied soul into a powerful, Spirit-filled, energized and determined personality of the apostles. Many Pentecostal Churches such as Living Faith, the Redeemed Christian Church of God, Powerful Bible Church, Mountain of Fire, Deeper Life Bible Church just a mention a few attested to the manifestation of the Holy Spirit before the eventual launching out of the evangelistic works carried out by the founders of these aforementioned church and their members. Hence the place of Holy in the founding of Pentecostal Churches is incontestable.

The Indigenous Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria such as Christ Apostolic Church, Cherubim and Seraphim, Celestial Church of Christ, and Church of the Lord believes in the Holy Spirit origin. Thus, Ayegboyin and Ishola (2013) referred these Churches as *Ijo Emi* (spiritual churches), where Holy Spirit is believed to feature prominently in their worship as he manifests through visions, interpretation of dreams, ecstatic behaviour and prophetic utterances. Oshitelu (2007) asserted that the rise of indigenous churches that could be regarded as forerunners of African Pentecostalism also arose from a number of other factors among which are the mode of organization in the mission churches –Anglican, Methodist and Baptist by foreign leaders who were imposed on the Africans. This was dictatorial attitude. The Africans were not allowed to lead organize the affairs of their churches. The Europeans treated the Africans as if they had no ability whatsoever to rule. They undermined their integrity.

The earliest origin of indigenous churches in Nigeria can be traced as far back as the 1918 in the St. Anglican Saviour Church, Ijebu-Ode with a group of prayer warriors called 'Diamond Stone'. This group eventually metamorphose into Christ Apostolic Church in 1943 (Oshun, 1981). Ayegboyin and Ishola (2013) provided a historical background of the origin of other indigenous churches such as Cherubim and Seraphim founded in 1925 as a prayer group which started in Lagos; Church of the Lord started with only ten people who attended its inauguration at Ogere in 1930; and Celestial Church of Christ founded in 1947.

It was observed that among these indigenous Churches in Ilorin Metropolis, Church leaders are usually occupied with different activities which include mid-week services and Sunday services. These churches are also fond of organising constant revivals which may tarry for weeks and possibly months. Due to this, the health conditions of these church leaders are not usually put into consideration. The results of these numerous church activities often lead to health challenges, sudden breakdown, ineffective church administration and mass movement of the youths from these churches to other neo-Pentecostal churches where youth are prioritised in the church administration.

Exegetical Analysis of Exodus 18:17-23

Verses 17-18: Moses' father-in-law replied, "What you are doing is not good." Jethro first comment after he had observed Mosaic leadership style was to make a remark that may seem negative to the audience but on the critical look of his statement, it portrayed good intention rather than the negative tone. Gill (n.d.) buttressed that the statement "what you are doing is not good". The Hebrew expression טוב לא (to tob) which literally translated to mean "not good" does not mean that it was not morally good, or that it was morally evil; for it was certainly a good thing to inquire of the mind and will of God for the people, and to hear and decide matters in controversy between them, and do justice to both parties; but it was not good for the health of Moses; it was not commodious and convenient for him; it was not for his bodily welfare; it was too much for him, as he explains himself in the next verse. Ellicot (n.d.) further buttressed on the verse 17 that Moses practice was unadvisable, both on his own account and on theirs. To keep suitors waiting all day, and perhaps finally dismiss them without their turn having come, was not fair upon them. The **verse 18** shows clearly Jethro's intention on the use of טוב לא in the verse 17. The **verse 18** shows a parallelism which is a common characteristic of Hebrew Poetry. תבול (tibbol) which is translated as 'will wear yourselves out' was expatiated in the parallel lines "the work is too heavy for you; you cannot handle it alone." This, however, portrays a coherent in the verses. According to Meyers (2005) the line of **verse 18** is a threefold declaration that portrayed that Moses caseload is too large.

Verse 19-21: The verse opens with the counselling session of Jethro. "Listen now to me and I will give you some advice (NIV)," indicate the tone of a counsellor and his counselee, which is common among in Israelites community; between God and man and vice versa (Prov. 8:32; Eze. 3:10; Job 37:14; Mt. 11:15). The first attention of the verse is a call to attention and consideration that is mostly needed between a father and his son, like the children of Israel is to God. Henry (2010) noted that Jethro thought the task was too much for Moses to undertake alone; also, it would make the administration of justice tiresome to the people. There may be over-doing even

in well-doing. According to Ryken and Hughes (2005) the initial of the verse shows that Jethro was preserving the role of the prophet. "...may God be with you" according to Matthew (n.d.), shows that a certain level of assurance which alleviate fears and doubt from His concept about God. He further went on to say that God is a God of order, and loves order; and he is a God of mercy, and would not have you destroy yourself in his work. Or it may be taken for a prayer, and God be with you, i.e. bless and assist thee therein.

Barnes (n.d) noted that **verse 20** "and you shall teach them the statutes and the decisions, and make them know the way in which they must walk and what they must do" (Revised Standard Version). The Hebrew word is emphatic, and signifies "enlightenment." The text gives four distinct points: the "ordinances," or specific enactments; "the laws," or general regulations," the way," the general course of duty; "the works," each specific act. **Verse 21** Keil and Delitzsch (n.d.) also went further to affirm that Moses was to select able men (חַיִל אֲנָשִׁים 'anšê ḥayil –men of moral strength, 1 Kings 1:52). The characters of the able men are, God-fearing, truthful and unselfish (gain-hating). The word rulers or overseers used in this passage is same as the one used in Deuteronomy 1:15 rendered 'captains' and not to be seen as the word rendered 'ruler' in Exodus 16:22. The word שָׂר (sar), when followed by 'of thousands', 'hundreds' is used only in connection with the army, being then rendered 'captain' (1 Samuel 8:12, 2 Kings 1:9: 'captains of tens,' however, occurs only here and Deuteronomy 1:15) (*Cambridge Bible for Schools*, n.d.).

Verse 22-23: The keywords of **verse 22** can be found in the expressions of; רַדְדָּבָר הַגָּדוֹל וְהַקָּטָן (*haqqaton haggadol haddabar*). The word קָטָן (*qaton*) means "small" or "minor" (Brown-Driver-Briggs, n.d.). Jethro suggests (*qaton dabar*) can be settled by appointed able men. It will also afford Moses the avenue to focus on (*hagadol dabar*) that require his urgent attention and wisdom. The Hebrew word דָּבָר (*dabar*) can mean both "thing" and "matter," and it is used here to refer to legal matters or disputes. Jethro's advice shows that not all matters require Moses' direct attention (Gary, n.d.). **Verse 23** Jethro ended his counseling thus, שְׁלוֹמֶם: אֵיבָב אֶיבָב מְקוֹמֹו עַל-הַהֵן מְהַעַע (*im et- haddabar hazzeh ta'she wesiweka elohim weyakalit amod wegam kal- haam hazzeh 'al- meqomow yabo besaliwim*). The phrase, ('*im elohim wesiweka*') indicates Jethro's counsel is subjected to God's commands. Although Jethro is a priest to God, he did not fully appreciate or understand all the God was able to do. So, he is trying not to be arrogant here, and saying, "Listen, this is your only solution" (Gary, n.d.).

Lessons for Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church Leaders in Ilorin Metropolis

There are lessons to be learnt by the Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church leaders in Ilorin Metropolis from the episode of Jethro and Moses in Exodus 18:17-23. Jethro was a good observer, listener and presenter. He observed the situation (Exo. 18:14a), listened to Moses' explanations (verse 15) and presented his counsel in a godly way (verses 19-23). These three attributes are highly commendable for Church leaders who would want to give counsel to counselees. In applying the lessons from Exodus 18:17-23, Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal Church leaders can create an environment where the Gospel is effectively shared, individuals are nurtured and empowered, and the church contributes positively to the spiritual and social

landscape of the nation. By embracing these principles, the Nigerian church can play a transformative role and serve as a beacon of light and hope in a diverse and dynamic society. Division of roles and tasks-sharing is identified in the passage. Jethro's counsel to Moses on task-sharing became a new form of Israelites policy even as they continue under the theocratic governance. The church today is made up of different people and functions that cannot be executed by an individual thus the need for concerted efforts by the make-up of the church. The pastor cannot be alone by himself the choir, usher, elder, Sunday school teacher, keyboardist and congregation. Therefore, it is pertinent to say that, church leaders must designate these functions to various members of their churches in order to ensure smooth service running. Jethro gave a prudent counsel as to the division of labour (verse 21-22) and universal experience in the Church and State has attested the soundness and advantages of the principle (Jameison et al., 1871).

Excessive tasks are hazardous to the health. Jethro's counsel showcases one with great concern about health issue. As a priest of Midian who must have served in that capacity for many years even before Moses' call, must have been aware of the health danger involve in Moses administrative policy hence call his attention to it. Church leaders must know and accept the fact that no one is indispensable. This means that, there is always a replacement for a person who is no longer active hence the need to be health conscious while in the service to God.

Appointment criteria must be defined and re-defined. The way church appointments are characterized by favouritism, nepotism, tribalism and affluence. Less emphasis is placed righteousness, infill of the Holy Spirit, wisdom and good ambassador of God through obedience to His words. Jethro's criteria for selection are godly approach which will enable continuity between God and the Israelites communities. Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal church leaders should teach God's decrees and instructions, way to congregation and how they are to behave. In addition, selected appointees should fear God, be trustworthy and hate dishonest gain. In a society often contending with issues of corruption and ethical challenges, the church has the responsibility to model the values it preaches.

Another important lesson to learn for the Jethro's counsel to Moses is the encouragement of mentoring. Tunji (2018) opines that mentoring produces leaders that ensure steadiness and preserve the culture and values of the institution because such leaders have not only been taught but also groomed and nurtured. They rise on the shoulders of their predecessors, and therefore are far more effective and visionary in administration. Thus, he further warned against godfatherism which is one of the menaces hindering church progress and effective leadership. Uroko (2020) lamented that the issue of capturing in Nigerian church has deteriorated. He stated that "unfortunately, mentorship has really gone sour amongst the pastoral ministry in Nigeria. Mentorship among Christian ministers in Nigeria is marred by many accusations and counter accusations". It is important to note that Nigeria Indigenous church leaders should encourage building capacities through raising mentees who will be useful in church administration.

Jethro's counsel is suitable for progress positioning, change desiring and goal-oriented venture. Nigerian church leaders can benefit from engaging in cross-cultural and interdenominational dialogue, gaining insights from other leaders, both within and beyond their nation's borders.

Also, every counsel must be godly and God's command. Jethro started with '...listen now to me' (verse 19) which shows that the counsel he was about to give is from his own perspective, perhaps an experience and concluded in verse 23 'if you do this and **God so commands...**' Moses needs to understand that what is superior to his counsel is God's instruction. Leaders of different capacities in Church must be cautious of counsel they receive and apply. All counsel must be godly and not contradict God's instruction hence the need to consult God before every act is taken.

Conclusion

Jethro's contribution to Mosaic leadership as revealed in Exo. 18:17-23 is relevant to Nigerian Indigenous Pentecostal church leaders in Ilorin Metropolis for effective health and wellbeing, encouragement of participation of Church members in church services and assignments, Church administration, and indeed for leaders in different segments in the society. These verses underscore the importance of effective leadership, job sharing, and the establishment of a structured and accountable system. In Jethro's suggestion, Moses cannot be the burden bearer alone as the Journey ahead is far and the assignment is tedious thus carrying the responsibilities alone will not only affect the health of Moses but also makes him to be ineffective. In a multi-church enterprise society like Nigeria where mega Churches are growing rapidly, the need for delegation of responsibility will not only create more chances for their successes but will also guarantee long life and foster unity within the church.

Recommendations

1. Division of responsibilities should be encouraged in among the Nigerian Pentecostal churches in Osun State in order to avert health hazard and promote church development
2. Mechanics such as organized system of leadership should be put in place in order to ensure good decision-making and conflict resolution within the ambit of the Church.
3. Selection for criteria into Church positions such as Deacon/Deaconess, Choir master, Sunday school teacher, Church secretary, Heads of Units amongst others should be defined and adhered. Pentecostal Church leaders must avoid all means of manipulation and favouritism in selection. This may jeopardise church growth and development.
4. The study also recommends that elites in the church should carefully encourage their Church leaders in other to avoid misunderstanding. For instance, in a situation where a church leader is illiterate, members should encourage such leader to enrol into a seminary for basic theological studies and administration. This may be enhanced by giving full or partial sponsorship to the leader with the aim that upon the completion of the programme, such leader would be able to apply the knowledge and administrative skills learnt in during the course of the programme.
5. In correcting an autocratic leader, a person giving such leader a counsel must first be humbled and ask for God's wisdom in what to say and how to present the case before the leader.
6. Godly elders in the church should be consulted before approaching any administrative issue. From a godly counsel, a proper recommendation may be given.

7. Pentecostal Church leaders must also acknowledge that a church is a civil society yet having Christ as its head. Therefore, leaders should also seek God like Solomon did in 1 Kg, 3:1-4 and got a blank cheque which enabled him to ask God for wisdom.

References

- Adesanya, O. I. (2019). "African Pentecostalism: Means to Salvation or Prosperity," in *African Pentecostalism*. Abeokuta: Crowther Theological Publishers.
- Ayegboyan, D. I. and Ishola, S. I. *African Indigenous Churches*. Kaduna: Prudent Universal Press & Publishing Co. Ltd., 2013.
- Barnes, (n.d.). "Barnes Notes on the Bible", Retrieved August 22, 2023 from <https://biblehub.com/commentaries/barnes/exodus/18.htm>
- Bill Mounce, (n.d.). "ἔξοδος". Retrieved May 10, 2024 from <https://www.billmounce.com/greekdictionary/exodus>
- Boaheng, I. (2021). *An African Background to the Old Testament*. Accra: Noyam Publishers.
- Brown-Driver-Briggs, (n.d.). "Brown-Driver-Briggs Hebrew Lexicon: rādāh". Retrieved August 20, 2023 from <https://www.bibletools.org/index.cfm/fuseaction/Lexicon.show/ID/H7287/radah.htm>
- Cambridge Bible for Schools and Colleges, (n.d.). "Exodus 18". Retrieved August 22, 2023 from <https://biblehub.com/commentaries/cambridge/exodus/18.htm>
- Ellicott, C.H. (n.d.). "Ellicott's Commentary for English Readers". Retrieved August 22, 2023 from <https://biblehub.com/commentaries/ellicott/exodus/18.htm>
- Enduring Word, "Exodus 18 – Jethro's Counsel to Moses". Retrieved August 21, 2023 from <https://enduringword.com/bible-commentary/exodus-18/>
- Francis, J. N. (1993). *Introduction to Administration of Guidance Services*. Benin: Barloz Publishers, Inc.
- Gary, K. (n.d.). "Exodus". Retrieved August 22, 2023 from <http://kukis.org/Exodus/Exodus18.htm>
- Gill, J. (n.d.). "Gill's Exposition to the Bible: Exodus 18". Retrieved August 21, 2023 from <https://biblehub.com/commentaries/gill/exodus/18.htm>
- Henry, M. (2010). *Matthew Henry's Concise Commentary on the Bible*. Grand Rapids, MI: Christian Classics Ethereal Library.
- Jamieson, R., Fausset, A.R. & Brown, D. (1871). *Commentary Critical and Explanatory on the Whole Bible*, PDF Version by: The eBible Study Library.
- Jeff, A.B. (n.d.). "How many came out of the exodus of Egypt". Retrieved August 20, 2023 from <https://ancient-hebrew.org/studies-interpretation/how-many-came-out-of-the-exodus-of-egypt.htm>
- Keil & Delitzsch, (n.d.). "Keil and Delitzsch OT Commentary". Retrieved August 20, 2023 from <https://biblehub.com/commentaries/kad/exodus/18.htm>
- Matthew, P. (n.d.). "Matthew Poole's Commentary: Exodus 18". Retrieved August 22, 2023 from <https://biblehub.com/commentaries/poole/exodus/18.htm>
- Merriam-Webster.com Dictionary, (n.d.). "Exodus". Retrieved August 22, 2023 from Merriam-Webster, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/exodus>
- Meyer, C. (2005). *Exodus*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- O' Connor, E. (1993). "Pentecostalism" in A. Richardson, and J. Bowen (eds.) *A New Dictionary of Christianity Theology*. London: SCM.
- Ogidiolu, A. O. (2019). "African Pentecostalism and the Old Testament Prophetic Heritage," in *African Pentecostalism*. Abeokuta: Crowther Theological Publishers.

- Oshitelu, G.A. (2007). *History of the Aladura Independent Churches 1918-1940: An Interpretation*. Ibadan: Hope Publications.
- Oshun, C. O. (1981) *Christ Apostolic Church of Nigeria: A Suggested Pentecostal Consideration of its Historical, Organisational, and Theological Developments, 1918-1975*. Ph.D thesis, University of Exeter.
- Redford, D. B. (1992). *Egypt, Canaan, and Israel in Ancient Times*. USA: Princeton University Press. ISBN 978-0-691-03606-9.
- Ryken, P.G. & Hughes, R.K. (2005). *Preaching the Word: Exodus Saved for God's Glory*. Illinois: Cross Way Books.
- Umaru, V. (2023). "Jethro's Methods of Leadership Development in Exodus 18:17-23: Lessons For Developing Sustainable Governance in Africa", Retrieved May 10, 2024 from <https://www.acjol.org/index.php/proceedings/article/download/4161/4077>
- Uroko, F. (2020). "Jethro's Mentoring of Moses (Exodus 18) and its Relevance to the Nigerian Clergy", *E-Journal of Religious and Theological Studies (ERATS)*, ISSN 2458 – 7338, Volume 6 Issue 2. <https://doi.org/10.32051/erats.2020.035>